

ADSORPTION OF VAPOURS ON SILICA GEL AT LOW PRESSURES

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Adsorption of ethyl alcohol and carbon tetrachloride at 25° on silica gel has been measured at reduced pressures with the help of a sensitive manometer. It has been found that the whole of the carbon tetrachloride in the adsorbed state may be confined to a two dimensional space which is not true for the adsorption of alcohol. The form of the Langmuir adsorption isotherm at low pressures has been considered and it is found that the Henry's law need not necessarily apply in these circumstances.

Measurements of adsorption in the pressure range of 0.1 to a few mm. of mercury are few in existence. The mercury manometer is not sufficiently sensitive to explore the adsorption in this region and conditions do not exist for the satisfactory working of such sensitive devices as the Pirani gauge or the viscosity gauges. In working with vapours little reliance can be put in the McLeod gauge. Though the experimental difficulties are considerable this region is of importance in understanding the nature of adsorption. For, secondary factors that set in due to increase of pressure are mainly absent so that the different equations of adsorption can be put to a more rigorous test than usual. It was with these intentions that the following measurements were undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used for these experiments is shown in Fig. 1. The mercury manometer used in previous measurements (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1945, **49**, 226) was replaced by one of oil

Fig. 1

(M) and was so arranged as to eliminate zero error. A liquid trap, cooled in solid carbon dioxide, was interposed between the apparatus and the pump. It prevented effectively

any vapour from reaching the latter. To measure the pressure inside the apparatus the pump was started and T_3 gradually opened, followed by T_2 . The zero error was thus kept down to the efficiency of the pump which was better than 10^{-2} mm. The difference in level on the two sides could be read directly on a scale rigidly attached to the manometer as usual with a telescope. An Apiezon oil of low density and moderate viscosity was chosen for use in the manometer. The density being 0.872, 1 mm. of oil = 0.0644 mm. of Hg or 1 mm. of mercury = 15.52 mm. of oil

The oil in the manometer was freed from dissolved air by pumping hard while the liquid was cautiously heated. The bulbs on M were meant for catching the copious froth produced. The vapours were swept out from the manometer after each measurement, the taps T_2 , T_3 being kept usually closed. One has to be careful in manipulating the taps, for a slight pressure difference between the two limbs may throw the oil violently on one side and thence into the main apparatus. It is also necessary to employ tubings of at least 4 mm. bore in constructing the manometer to prevent the oil column from breaking at times.

Two samples of silica gel described previously (Thesis, London, 1947, p. 25) have been used. One sample, UCL F, prepared at the University College, London, was about three months old and had been evacuated for 2 hours at 300° - 320° . The other sample, Patna H, prepared at Patna, was three years old and had been evacuated at the same temperature. Uniform electrical heating was employed in each case. The gel was flushed several times with vapour before commencement of the first run. The whole apparatus was maintained at 25° throughout these measurements.

Fig. 2

The results of these measurements are shown graphically in Figs. 2, 3 and 4. Fig. 2 shows the plot of the amount of adsorption per unit weight of the gel, x/m , expressed in g. mol. of

the liquid $\times 10^4$, against pressure p in mm. of oil. The forms of the isotherms are the same as obtained earlier with a mercury manometer in the same pressure range. Also, the amounts of adsorption at corresponding pressures in the two sets of data are substantially the same (Gyani, Thesis, London, 1947, p.19 and Fig. 11). Saturation has not set in yet in the range of these pressures.

D I S C U S S I O N

The low pressure measurements with alcohol establish the existence of the initial, almost vertical rise of the $x/m-p$ isotherm at pressures too small to measure (McBain, "Sorption of Gases and Vapours", p.128 *et seq.*, London, 1932). The upper limit of this pressure could not be larger than 0.006 mm. of mercury, since such a pressure could no doubt have been detected if not measured on the oil manometer. It is also proved with certainty that no appreciable quantity of carbon tetrachloride is retained by either gel at low pressures. Fig. 2

Fig. 3

shows that the plot of x/m against p does not approximate to a straight line even when one confines oneself to pressures as low as 50 mm. of oil which corresponds to only 3 mm. of mer-

cury, but this fact as commonly supposed is not against the applicability of the Langmuir adsorption equation as shown below.

Fig. 3 shows the plot of $\frac{p}{x/m}$ against p for both the compounds. The curves have a curvature concave towards the pressure side which is only slight in the case of alcohol but strong in the case of carbon tetrachloride. The data are therefore not in agreement with the Langmuir equation. To test the present data for a fit with the classical adsorption equation, $\log x/m$ has been plotted against $\log p$ for both the compounds in Fig. 4. The alcohol isotherm has a smaller slope than the one for carbon tetrachloride, but each is a satisfactory straight line in the range of these measurements. One may conclude that the classical equation fits the data much more satisfactorily than the Langmuir equation. It may be of interest to point out that separate experiments have shown that the heat of adsorption of carbon tetrachloride on silica gel is particularly variable with the amount of adsorption (Gyani, Thesis, London, 1947, p.103). The heat of adsorption fell from 9344 cal. per mol. of the liquid to 8782 as the amount of adsorption was decreased from 50.10×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. of the gel to 35.80. This variation is not recognised in the simple deduction of the Langmuir equation.

Fig. 4

Another point of interest in these measurements concerns the slopes of the $\log x/m$ — $\log p$ curves. The slopes are equal in the case of each vapour irrespective of the adsorbent. The slope of the CCl_4 curve is very close to $2/3$, whilst that of the alcohol curves is about 0.2 . If the previously expressed view of the author regarding the classical equation (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1945, 49, 442) is correct, one has to conclude that the carbon tetrachloride molecules may be strictly confined to a two-dimensional space in the adsorbed state. The fact that the theoretical and the observed values of the slope agree so closely should be related to the observation that there is no initial anomaly *i.e.* a vertical rise of the x/m — p curve at $p \rightarrow 0$, such

as is seen to occur with alcohol. One can therefore understand why the value of the slope in the case of alcohol is not significant. A part of the alcohol is obviously held by the gel very rigidly and is probably of the point-adsorbed type (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1945, 49, 442).

Form of the Langmuir Isotherm at low Pressures

Consider the slope of the Langmuir adsorption isotherm

$$x/m = \frac{\alpha\beta p}{1 + \beta p} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

at the point p . The slope $\equiv \frac{d(x/m)}{dp} = \frac{\alpha\beta}{(1 + \beta p)^2} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$

The rate of change of this slope at any pressure p is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2(x/m)}{dp^2} &= \frac{d}{dp} \left[\frac{\alpha\beta}{(1 + \beta p)^2} \right] \text{ from (2)} \\ &= - \frac{2\alpha\beta}{(1 + \beta p)^3} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

We find from (3) that if the slope of the isotherm is small, it is most strongly curved near the origin. This result contradicts the usual statement that the isotherm should become linear as p approaches low values. This statement is based on an approximate reasoning adopted by Langmuir himself (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2221).

A general expression for the radius of curvature r of the isotherm at a point p may be written down as

$$r = \frac{1 + \left[\frac{d(x/m)}{dp} \right]^2}{\frac{d^2(x/m)}{dp^2}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Substituting appropriate values from (2) and (3) in (4),

$$r = \frac{(1 + \beta p)^4 + \alpha^2 \beta^2}{2\alpha\beta^2 (1 + \beta p)^3}$$

neglecting the negative sign. One can see readily that the condition that r be a minimum *i.e.* the isotherm be curved most, is

$$p = \frac{\sqrt[4]{3\alpha^2\beta^2} - 1}{\beta} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

It is quite possible therefore that the pressure at which the isotherm is curved most, may be close to the zero pressure, the actual value being determined by the constants α and β . Large values of β are particularly unfavourable to the validity of Langmuir's relevant statement which is apparent from an examination of (1) itself.

It is seen from Fig. 2 that the isotherms have their strongest curvatures well within 50 mm. of oil (or 3 mm. of Hg). The isotherms therefore deviate most strongly from Henry's law within the range of these low pressures, but this fact by itself does not rule out the applicability of the Langmuir equation as may be found frequently stated in literature.

The fact that the deviations from straight line graphs in Fig. 3 are at least qualitatively in favour of the classical equation

$$x/m = k \cdot p^{1/n} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

is demonstrated from the following consideration. In obtaining the value of the slope of the $\frac{p}{x/m} - p$ curve from (6) one gets

$$\frac{d}{dp} \left(\frac{p}{x/m} \right) = \frac{d}{dp} \left(\frac{p}{K \cdot p^{1/n}} \right) = \frac{n-1}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{x/m} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) shows that the slope of the curve is not constant but decreases as the amount of adsorption increases *i.e.* as the pressure increases, which is the fact actually observed.

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